

Determination of cephalosporins using sulphide ion selective membrane electrode

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Abstract : The present paper describes the methods of analysis of cephalosporins which is based on alkaline degradation of respective cephalosporins which results in quantitative formation of sulphide ions. The resulting sulphide ion was titrated against a standard solution of lead nitrate in presence of glycerol. For monitoring the titration a heterogeneous precipitate based sulphide ion selective electrode was prepared using PVC as an inert binder. The characteristics of the electrode, namely electrode response, response time, working pH range, selectivity coefficients in presence of closely associated anions were determined. It was found that the electrode is selective towards S^{2-} in presence of several divalent and monovalent anions. The determination of cephalosporins by titration method using the electrode prepared were further confirmed by spectrophotometry.

Keywords : Cephalosporins, sulphide ion, selective membrane electrode.

Introduction

A group of antibiotics which is known as cephalosporins are special class of β -lactum antibiotic and are used in the treatment of typhoid, meningitis and several other types of infections. β -Lactum ring is fused through the nitrogen and the adjacent tetrahedral carbon atoms to a second heterocyclic ring. In case of cephalosporin it is a six membered dihydrothiazine ring. Cephalosporins are generally 3-acetoxymethyl-7-acylamino-3-cephem-4-carboxylic acids. They are semi-synthetic antibiotics¹.

In the present work cephalixin, cefuroxime and ceftriaxone were chosen for finding out the method for their determination using ion selective electrode. Cephalixin is given for treating infection of the respiratory and urinary tract and other infections because of the sensitive organisms. Cefuroxime is given in the treatment of meningitis, respiratory tract, genito-urinary tract, skin and soft tissue infections and used as prophylaxis against infections in surgical procedures. Ceftriaxone is also given in the treatment of meningitis, septicaemia, typhoid and urinary tract infections and prophylaxis in surgical infections^{2,3}.

Accurate monitoring is an essential part of quality

control programme, drug delivery strategies and pharmacokinetics studies. Although extensive attention has been paid over the analysis of pure antibiotics, there is still need for development of certain sensitive methods with higher stake in terms of selectivity and detection limit. Various procedures have been employed for this purpose. During the past thirty years, there has been an unprecedented activity in the field of analytical techniques in the context of assay of drugs. A detailed literature survey reveals about some of the prime techniques adopted for the analysis of cephalosporins which are summarized in the following paragraphs.

Fogg *et al.*⁴⁻⁶ carried out alkaline degradation of cephalosporins and after that it can be determined titrimetrically. Kane and Boparai⁷ used alkalimetric titration method for the determination of cephalixin. Dubey and Shukla⁸ proposed a new titrimetric method for the determination of cephalixin and cefuroxime in pharmaceutical dosage form using pyridinium chlorochromate.

Abdel-Khalek and Mahrous⁹ used ammonium molybdate for the colorimetric determination of cephalosporins. A number of review articles¹⁰⁻¹⁴ have been published, describing the colorimetric determinations of cepha-

losporins using different reagents.

O'Hever^{15,16} discussed the potential of derivative spectrophotometry in his two review articles. Several review articles¹⁷⁻²⁷ appeared in the mean time covering details about the spectrophotometric procedures developed for the determination of cephalosporins. A RP-HPLC²⁸ and voltametric²⁹ determination of cephalosporin in pharmaceutical and biological fluids were also carried out.

However, a few papers^{30,31} have been published describing the potentiometric determination of cephalosporins.

No work has been reported in the literature about the determination of cephalosporins using ion selective electrode. Ion selective electrodes have been reported for the determination of sulphide ions. They are either homogeneous^{32,33} involving Ag₂S alone or heterogenous based on Ag₂S in silicon rubber matrix or polypropylene matrix³⁴⁻³⁷.

In the present investigation an attempt has been made to determine three different drug of cephalosporanic group using a novel sulphide membrane ion selective electrode. This electrode was used for the first time for potentiometric determination of three drugs of cephalosporin group in pure and in pharmaceutical formulations.

The cephalosporin molybdophosphoric acid complex was also investigated using spectrophotometry and applied for the determination of three different cephalosporin present in pharmaceutical formulation, so that these determinations, could be compared with the values obtained from electrochemical sensors.

Results and discussion

Electrometric method :

After conditioning the electrode (the electrode was dipped in 1.0×1.0^{-1} mol dm⁻³ solution of sodium sulphide for 24 h before use) the electrode potential for a series of standard solution in the concentration range 1.0×10^{-1} to 1.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ were measured with the help of sulphide membrane ion selective electrode and a

calomel electrode as a reference electrode. A linear response was observed for S²⁻ concentration down to 1×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³. The slope was found to be 28 mV per decade change in S²⁻ ion concentration.

In order to find out the response time of the electrode, the electrode was first dipped in 1.0×10^{-1} mol dm⁻³ solution of the S²⁻ ion and suddenly the concentration of solution was changed to 1.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³. The value of potential changes were noted at the interval of every 5 s. A constant potential was obtained after 15 s.

To study the effect of pH, the pH of the 1.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ Na₂S solution was varied by the addition of NaOH or HCl. It was found that the potential remain unchanged within the pH range 3 to 10 (working range).

The selectivity coefficient for different anions for S²⁻ ions were determined by mixed solution method^{38,39}. For this the concentration of S²⁻ ion was varied while the concentration of interfering ion was kept constant at 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³.

The electrode is selective in presence of several closely associated anions (Table 1).

The life time of the electrode was found to be 40 weeks of its fabrication.

Application :

To explore the utility of the electrode prepared, the electrode was used as an indicator electrode in the determination of three different cephalosporins in pure form and in pharmaceutical preparations viz. cephalexin, cefuroxime and ceftriaxone.

Principle :

The method of determination of cephalosporins is based on alkaline degradation⁴⁰ of respective cephalosporin and as a result of which quantitative amount of sulphide ions are produced in solution. The quantitative estimation of sulphide ion was carried out by titrating the solution with standard lead nitrate solution using prepared sulphide ion selective membrane electrode and SCE as a reference electrode.

Table 1. Electrode selectivity coefficients, determined by mixed solution method

Anions	Cl ⁻	Br ⁻	I ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	CO ₃ ²⁻	C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	SO ₃ ²⁻	NO ₃ ⁻	CH ₂ COO ⁻	SCN ⁻
Selectivity coefficient	0.1	0.05	0.05	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.036	0.01	0.01	0.05

Lead nitrate was used instead of silver nitrate for the titration of sulphide ions mainly because there is less absorption of sulphide ion on lead sulphide than on silver sulphide. The addition of glycerol increased the stability of the potential readings.

Procedure for the analysis of three different cephalosporins in pure form and in formulations (viz. cephalalexin, cefuroxime and ceftriaxone) :

For the analysis of pure sample of cephalosporin, 100 mg finely powdered drug was dissolved in 100 mL, 1.0×10^{-1} mol dm⁻³ sodium hydroxide solution containing 20 g L⁻¹ ascorbic acid and degradation of drug was carried out by the method as described above⁴⁰. Solution obtained after degradation was titrated against 1.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ of lead nitrate solution using sulphide selective membrane electrode as an indicator electrode. Magnetic stirrer was used for stirring the solution during the titration. The same procedure was repeated with other two samples of cephalosporins.

For alkaline degradation of formulated cephalosporin, cephalalexin, 20 capsules of the drug was taken and mixed thoroughly. Similarly for cefuroxime 20 tablets were grounded to fine powder and 100 mg of drugs were subjected to alkaline degradation. In case of ceftriaxone 20 vials of injections were taken (100 mg) and subjected to alkaline degradation. The degraded solution of all the three formulations were titrated potentiometrically using sulphide selective membrane electrode as an indicator electrode and SCE as reference electrode. The value of concentration of analyte was found out from the titration curve for pure as well as for pharmaceutical formulations. Three different titrations were performed with different volumes of aliquot. The results of determination of cephalosporins in pure form and pharmaceutical formulations in different samples are summarized in the Table 2.

Spectrophotometric method :

Determination of wavelength of maximum absorption :

To determine the wavelength of maximum absorption different solutions were prepared for different cephalosporins. Three different solutions were prepared by 5 mL of drug solution (1 mg/mL), 5 mL of 1.0×10^{-1} sulphuric acid and 5 mL of 1% molybdophosphoric acid in 25 mL test tube. The solutions were mixed by shaking and then

Table 2. Results of determination of cephalosporin in pure form and in pharmaceutical formulations

Sl. no.	Sample	Aliquot taken (mL)	Amount obtained (mg)
1.	Cephalexin (Pure) (Deys Medical Pvt. Ltd.)	20	19.79
		25	24.84
		30	29.85
	Ceflin 500 (Cap) (Franklin Remedies)	20	19.20
		25	24.32
		30	29.30
2.	Cefuroxime (Pure) (Gracure Pvt. Ltd., Rajasthan)	20	19.65
		25	24.55
		30	29.56
	Cefakind (Tab) (Makind Pharma Pvt. Ltd.)	20	19.13
		25	24.23
		30	29.18
3.	Ceftriaxone (Gracure Pvt. Ltd., Rajasthan)	20	19.40
		25	24.54
		30	29.30
	Zefor-100 (I) (Zee Drugs)	20	19.19
		25	23.92
		30	29.15

Cap – Capsule; Tab – Tablet; I – Injection.

placed for 25 min in a water bath thermostated at 95.5 ± 0.5 °C. After completion of the heat treatment, the solution was cooled immediately to room temperature using the cold water bath.

The resulting solution was transferred carefully and quantitatively into a 25 mL volumetric flask and diluted to the mark with double distilled water. The flasks were allowed to stand for 15 min under light protected conditions at room temperature for optimum development and stabilization of colour. After that the absorbance of each solution was measured at interval of 10 nm in the wavelength region 500–740 nm against blank treated similarly. It was observed that wavelength of maximum absorption for all the solutions of antibiotic was 715 nm.

A series of solutions for all the three cephalosporins were prepared separately in the concentration range 25–100 µg/mL using the procedure described above. Absorbance of these solutions were measured at 715 nm against a blank treated similarly. Absorbance values were plotted against concentrations of antibiotics and it was observed that system obeys Beer's law. The Sandell's sensitivity were also determined (Table 3).

Table 3. Determination of different cephalosporins in their pharmaceutical formulations using calibration curve

Sl. no.	Sample	Aliquots taken (mL)	Absorbance (A)	Amount obtained (mg)	Avg. (mg)	Std. dev.	Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)
1.	Cephalexin Ceflin 500 (Cap) (Franklin Remedies)						
	C ₁	2.1	0.410	24.78			
	C ₂	2.3	0.425	24.50			
	C ₃	2.4	0.475	24.50	24.58	0.12	0.1462
	C ₃	2.5	0.501	24.57			
	C ₅	2.7	0.550	24.55			
2.	Cefuroxime Cefakind-250 (Tab) (Mankind Pharma Pvt. Ltd.)						
	C ₁	1.4	0.385	24.30			
	C ₂	1.6	0.451	24.40			
	C ₃	1.8	0.500	24.28	24.33	0.024	0.1242
	C ₃	2.2	0.550	24.30			
	C ₅	2.4	0.635	24.30			
3.	Ceftriaxone Zefor-100 (I)(Zee Drugs)						
	C ₁	1.0	0.425	24.58			
	C ₂	1.2	0.511	24.49			
	C ₃	1.4	0.585	24.53	24.56	0.055	0.1320
	C ₃	1.6	0.651	24.65			
	C ₅	1.8	0.751	24.59			

Cap – Capsule; Tab – Tablet; I – Injection, Average of 5 determinations.

Table 4. Comparison of results obtained by potentiometric and spectrophotometric methods for different pharmaceutical samples of cephalosporins

Sl. no.	Sample	Amount	Amount obtained (mg)	
			Electrode	Spectrophotometry
1.	Cephalexin Ceflin 500 (Cap) (Franklin Remedies)	25	24.48	24.58
2.	Cefuroxime Cefakind-250 (Tab) (Mankind Pharma Pvt. Ltd.)	25	24.25	24.37
3.	Ceftriaxone Zefor-100 (I) (Zee Drugs)	25	23.92	24.56

The determination of cephalosporins content from pharmaceutical formulations by electrochemical method as well as spectrophotometric method (Table 4) for a given amount shows fairly good agreement in the values.

Experimental

Reagents :

All the chemicals used were of A.R. or G.R. grades of E. Merck, B.D.H., Thomas Bakers or Qualigens. Antibiotics viz. cephalexim [Deys Medicals Pvt. Ltd. (Allahabad)], cefuroxime and ceftriaxone [both Gracure

Pvt. Ltd. (Rajasthan)]. The pharmaceutical formulations of antibiotics taken are as follows : cephalexin capsule (Ceflin-500 – Franklin Remedies), cefuroxime (Tablet), (Cefakind 250 – Mankind Pharma Pvt. Ltd.), ceftriaxone (Injection) (Zefor 100 – Zee Drug). Ion free double distilled water was used throughout the experiment.

Instruments :

A Philips pH/mV meter (Model 9405 m) with a silver-silver chloride electrode as a reference electrode was used for the measurement of electrode potential. A digital pH meter (Century CP901) with combined electrode was used

for pH measurements. Spectrophotometric data were obtained using a digital UV-Visible spectrophotometer (SICO Feedback) with 10 mm quartz cuvettes. All measurements were carried out at room temperature (25 ± 2 °C).

Preparation of electroactive material and membrane :

The silver sulphide precipitate was used as an electroactive material for the preparation of the membrane. 200 mg of this substance was mixed with PVC (100 mg) in 6 mL tetrahydrofuran (THF) and finally mixed with 2 drops of dioctylphthalate. Resulting solution was cast into a glass casting tube and left for slow evaporation to get a thin membrane. A portion of the membrane of appropriate size was cut from the master membrane and was mounted at the lower end of the glass tube (diameter 1 cm and length 15 cm) and it was dried for 24 h. The tube was filled with 0.01 mol dm^{-3} sulphide ion solution and kept immersed in sulphide ion solution of 0.1 mol dm^{-3} for one week. The internal reference electrode was Ag-AgCl and external reference electrode was calomel electrode.

The entire electrode system for the measurement can be represented as :

Internal reference electrode Ag-AgCl	Internal reference solution (0.01 mol dm^{-3} sodium sulphide)	Sulphide(II) ion selective membrane	Sample solution	External reference electrode (SCE)
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Before making measurements the electrode assembly was dipped in 0.1 mol dm^{-3} solution of Na_2S for 24 h.

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